

Complex Adaptive Systems as an Idealized State A Conceptual Critique of Complexity Leadership

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Abstract

This article offers a conceptual critique of the use of complex adaptive systems (CAS) in complexity leadership studies. Although CAS has become a central construct in this literature, its application is often assumed rather than examined. Drawing on established CAS criteria (Benbya & McKelvey, 2006), the paper evaluates whether commonly cited examples such as teams, healthcare, organizations, traffic, and weather actually meet the defining features of CAS. The analysis shows that, apart from sensitivity to initial conditions, these examples seldom satisfy the criteria and that leading texts in the field contain internal inconsistencies in their treatment of CAS. The findings suggest that CAS should be regarded less as an existing organizational reality and more as an idealized state or latent potential that organizations may approximate under specific conditions. By clarifying these limits, the paper strengthens theoretical rigor in complexity leadership and highlights the need to distinguish metaphorical from empirical use.

Keywords: Complex adaptive systems, complexity science, complexity leadership, organizations, self-organizing, teams.

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Introduction

The influence of complexity science on organizational science started in the mid- to late-1980s; however, as it relates to leadership, its application did not gain traction and legitimacy until the publication of Uhl-Bien and her colleagues' work (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007; Uhl-Bien & Marion, 2008). Complexity leadership is touted as a solution to the ever-increasing complexity of today's environment, what is often referred to as wicked problems (Rittel & Webber, 1973), adaptive challenges (Heifetz, 1994), the poly- (Tooze, 2022) and meta-crisis (Hunt, 2022).

Complexity leadership imports several concepts from complexity science, such as complex adaptive system (CAS), edge of chaos, attractors, and self-organizing. However, with few exceptions (e.g., Author, xxxx) its assumptions and language have not been critically examined.

Using a conceptual critique, this paper examines one of the central concepts in complexity leadership—namely, the complex adaptive system (CAS)—and critically evaluates its use. First, it assesses the most commonly cited examples in the complexity leadership literature against established CAS criteria. Second, it highlights inconsistencies within the statements made by seminal authors, demonstrating tensions in how CAS is defined and applied in the field. In doing so, the paper clarifies the limits of CAS as an organizing concept in complexity leadership and argues that it should be understood as an idealized state or latent potential rather than an inherent organizational reality.

Complex Adaptive Systems

A CAS is the basic unit of analysis in complexity science (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007). It is defined as “Neural-like networks of interacting, interdependent agents who are bonded in a cooperative dynamic by common goal, outlook, need, and so on” (Uhl-Bien et al., 2008, p. 201). A CAS is made up of interdependent, interacting, semi-autonomous agents who create a systems-wide pattern (Quade & Holladay, 2010). Examples of CAS frequently used in the literature include teams (Pyepa et al., 2018), healthcare systems (Covvey, 2018), organizations (Schneider & Somers, 2006,), and weather (McKelvey, 2008).

Benbya and McKelvey (2006) identified eight characteristics of CAS: a large number of components, diversity and variation, nonlinearity and unpredictability, adaptation to the environment, interactions between agents, self-organization, and dependence on initial conditions. Table 1 examines the degree to which each of these characteristics apply to the examples used in the literature.

CAS example	Large number of components	Diversity and variation	Nonlinearity And unpredictability	Adaptation to the environment	Interactions between agents	Self-organization	Dependence on initial conditions
Teams	N	Sometimes	Limited	Rare	Y	Possible	Y
Healthcare systems	Y	Sometimes	Rare	Rare	Y if small world network. N if large world network	Only some parts might be able to self-organize.	Y
Organizations	Medium to large ones	Sometimes	Rare	Somewhat	Y if small world network. N if large world network	Unlikely at the organizational level. Can occur at in isolated locals.	Y
Traffic systems	Y	Y	Y	N	Y if small world network. N if large world network	Y	Y
Weather	Somewhat	N	Y	N	N	N	Y

Let us examine each entry in the table and assess the degree to which it fits the criteria for CAS.

- **Teams:** Teams can vary in size; whether a team has three or 20 members, this is far from the large number of agents required for a CAS. Some teams can be very diverse while others are not. Also, not all types of diversity are conducive to team functioning. For example, demographic category differences can lead to more conflict (Mannix & Neale, 2005) and by extension can hinder functioning as a CAS. There is a limited amount of unpredictability within a team's work. This will depend on the team's task with certain kinds of contexts resulting in higher unpredictability. Given organizational constraints, it is questionable whether a team can adapt to the external environment. Teams can have a high degree of interaction, but this can depend on colocation versus being geographically dispersed. Also, teams can be dysfunctional (Lencioni, 2007) and having low trust and high conflict can lead to a breakdown of interaction. The degree to which a team can self-organize is somewhat debatable. A team of the 2-3 individuals might have limited options for self-organizing. Moreover, a team with a high degree of specialization might face issues with self-organizing; each person would have to remain within their area of specialization. Finally, teams do display a degree of sensitivity to initial conditions. For instance, a change in the skills or identity of one member during team formation can lead to marked changes in performance over time.
- **Healthcare:** Healthcare in the United States is made up of insurance companies, doctors, nurses, patients, patient family members, technicians, communities, pharmaceutical companies, and government, thus it meets the first criterion of large

numbers of agents. Variation and diversity are likely as the US becomes more diverse. Moreover, there are many kinds of agents like doctors, nurses, physician assistants, patients, staff, government officials, and so on. As for unpredictability and nonlinearity, a high level of unpredictability in healthcare systems at the national scale might only be present during black swan events like the COVID pandemic. Regarding adaptability to external environment, a cursory examination of the healthcare system in the United States would find limited adaptability as costs keep rising and service quality remains the same or worsens. When it comes to interactions among agents, there is an assumption that system with a large number of agents such as healthcare will have plenty of interactions among agents. However, there are two issues here: 1) the perennial problem of silos prevalent in most organizations 2) the difference between small and large world networks (Watts & Strogatz, 1998); small-world networks are networks in which an agent or node is connected to a small number of agents or nodes in its immediate vicinity, but also to a few agents or nodes that are far away. These long-range connections help reduce the overall distance between nodes in the network. Large-world networks, on the other hand, are networks where an agent or node is connected mostly to agents or nodes in its immediate vicinity, with few or no connections to agents or nodes that are far away. Healthcare has more of the characteristic of a large world network and thus the interaction tends to be more local preventing the system from becoming a CAS. A healthcare system like the one in the United States is unlikely to self-organize at the system level. Laws, and structures (bureaucracy) are in place to prevent this from happening. However, some part of the healthcare system might exhibit self-organizing (e.g., teams). Finally, sensitivity to initial conditions is present; had the system started a single payer as opposed to multi-payer, it would look and perform very differently.

- Organizations: It should go without saying that a small family business of 15 employees, and a few suppliers, with a simple supply chain, does not meet the first criterion. It is only as the organization increases in size that it can start to meet this criterion. As with teams, variation and diversity will vary from organization to organizations, with some organizations being more homogeneous than others. For example, an engineering company might have 70-90% of the staff as engineers, 80-90% of them male, and 80-90% White. Unpredictability and nonlinearity might apply to organizations, especially as they get larger. The dismal survival rate of organizations: only a third of business last for 10 years or more (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024) indicates that on average organizations *fail to adapt*. As with healthcare the degree to which the interactions will lead to CAS will depend on the network setting within the organization. Similar to a healthcare system, localized self-organization can happen. However, large scale organizational level self-organizing is very unlikely. Finally, organizations display a high degree of dependence on initial conditions and small differences in a single variable at the inception of an organization can lead to large differences in performance later on.
- Traffic systems: The first criterion is met as traffic systems contain a large number of agents. Whether or not these agents can be considered diverse will depend on our view. If we focus on who is operating the different vehicles (cars, trucks, etc.) then there will be all kinds of diversity (age, sex, gender, race, etc.). The type of vehicle also has a role to play and the diversity of vehicle size can impact the behavior of the whole system. So overall, one can conclude that the second criterion is also met. Traffic systems can behave in a none-linear and unpredictable manner; all of sudden, traffic can come

to a standstill for no discernable reason. In traffic systems, identifying an “environment” to which adaptation occurs is problematic. Vehicles adapt to one another in real time, but the system as a whole does not display meaningful adaptation to a broader environment. The persistence of traffic congestion in cities such as Los Angeles, Cairo, and Paris suggests that adaptation, when it occurs, is transient and insufficient to alter long-term system behavior. The cars are only adapting to one another. As for self-organizing, it could potentially happen when there is no interference from the traffic police. However, self-organizing in the case of traffic does not lead to organizing to a higher level of complexity. Finally, traffic systems are sensitive to initial conditions. For example, if just a few people left to work a few minutes later or earlier, the behavior of the whole system can change.

- Weather: The weather involves multiple interacting components, including temperature, ocean currents, humidity, solar radiation, wind, atmospheric pressure, cloud formations, and landforms. It is somewhat questionable whether these can reach the numbers that qualify designating the weather as a CAS. As for diversity of agents, the interacting components are just that and for this author do not qualify as agents. Weather systems display a degree of unpredictability and nonlinearity and this is very evident in extreme weather events like hurricanes, tornadoes, and snow storms in the middle of desert. Similar to traffic systems, the concept of adapting to the environment is meaningless in the context of the weather. Similarly, it is hard to imagine what importing the concept of interacting between agents looks like in the context of the weather. Sure pressure, temperature, and humidity do interact, but they not networked as either a small or large

world network in the same way one would find in organizations, healthcare systems, or even some large teams. Also, the concept of self-organizing in context of weather is meaningless. The components of the weather cannot self-organize to a higher level of complexity. Finally, the weather is sensitive to the initial conditions of each of its components. There is plenty of interactions between agents.

From the outgoing analysis, none of the examples used in the literature, including organizations, met the full criteria for CAS. The only criterion that was consistently met was sensitivity to initial conditions. All other criteria were either unmet or were met only under certain conditions. It is also noteworthy that adapting to the environment, the *raison d'etre* of CAS, was mostly absent in the cited examples.

Perhaps applying strict criteria to designate something as a CAS is an unfair and biased practice. However, there is evidence from the complexity leadership literature that affirms the earlier conclusion *vis-à-vis* organizations; leading complexity leadership scholars tell us that organizations are “transformational engines that generate opportunities for members to learn from each other and from organizational resources such as data bases [*sic*], procedures, and goals” (Kilduff et al., 2008, p. 99). Moreover, supposedly CASs “are capable of solving problems creatively and are able to learn and adapt quickly” (Uhl-Bien et al., 2008, p. 201). Why would we need complexity leadership and its attempts to move systems and organizations to the edge of chaos (so that it can become a CAS) to

increase creativity, learning, and problem solving if organizations were already CAS? Why would we need to use “a mesolevel model that integrates complex adaptive systems CAS and bureaucracy.” (Uhl-Bien, & Marion, 2008, p. 8) if organization was already a CAS. This attempt at integration would not make any sense. Can organizations simply become CAS simply by changing their response as Ashmos et al. (2000) suggest “organizations that see their environments as turbulent and complex, but in some cases choose relatively simple, mechanistic managerial responses and in other cases choose managerial responses that are more consistent with the characteristics of complex adaptive systems” (p. 577). Does this not suggest that organizations are not already CAS and it is through their shift in perspective and subsequent actions that they become CAS?

Discussion

Organizations are typically structured to suppress novelty that falls outside established paradigms. This structural tendency limits the extent to which they can exhibit CAS-like properties, except in highly specific or temporary circumstances. The CAS concept, like other concepts in complexity leadership is often taken for granted. However, the table analysis and the inconsistencies outlined in the quotes in the previous paragraph suggest that organizations generally do not function as CAS. Instead, CAS should be understood as an *idealized state* or a *latent potential* that organizations may occasionally approximate but rarely sustain. Notable exceptions exist: for example, military units in the midst of battle or organizational interventions such as world cafés can temporarily display CAS-like properties. However, these remain contingent, episodic, and context-dependent rather than enduring organizational features.

Using the concept of CAS is still useful; Overman (as cited in Lissack, 1999, p. 113) argued that:” the new sciences of chaos and quantum theory[complexity] offer valuable metaphors and methods that can challenge the management research agenda into the next century.” Uhl-Bien and Marion’s (2009) provide their justification for approaching leadership from a CAS perspective: “it offers a paradigm for thinking about leadership from which we can more easily explore issues that confound us from a traditional view— issues of shared, distributed, collective, relational, dynamic, emergent and adaptive leadership processes” (p. 631).

Nevertheless, Hazy et al. (2007) point out that “although emergence, and its cousin self-organization, are perhaps the most closely associated with complexity, they are also among the most widely misused ideas in the field.” (p. 8). One can also add CAS to this short list of closely associated and widely misused concepts. Glenda Eoyang (2009) in the introduction to her book *Coping with Chaos: Seven Simple Tools* writes “At no point will I weigh you down with scientific detail or mathematical rigor. At some points, I will take liberties with the scientific concepts as I apply them metaphorically to organizational and management behavior.” (p. vi) This poses at least two difficulties: 1) Social scientists can have partial or sometimes distorted interpretations of scientific phenomena, in the process ignoring important aspects of their application. For example, conducting a network analysis to assess the type of network present before assuming that having a large number of agents leads always to more global interactions. 2) Some of these concepts do not translate well unless they are considered as metaphors. Leadership scholars, thus, need to better develop their scientific

understanding. Moreover, they need to take less liberty with scientific concepts and declare when they use such concepts as metaphors versus a fact.

A related issue is that complexity leadership can at times move too quickly from heterogeneity and increased interaction to expectations of learning, adaptation, and emergent order. In practice, these outcomes depend on more than interaction alone.

Organizational actors may differ not only in perspective or expertise, but in something more foundational: their underlying ways of being(ontology), their implicit assumptions about authority and knowledge, and their operative purposes. Organizations are rarely unified by a single telos. Often, managers, frontline workers, specialists, and administrators may pursue ends that are formally aligned but functionally divergent (Cyert & March, 1963) , and these divergences are usually tacit rather than declared. When complexity leadership interventions introduce simple rules, increase connectivity, or attempt to create conditions at the edge of chaos, they are, in effect, releasing these latent tensions rather than resolving them. Multiple and sometimes competing teloi do not disappear under conditions of increased interaction; they surface, collide, and redirect emergent processes in ways that neither leaders nor models anticipate (Merton, 1936). The result is not the coherent adaptive order that CAS imagery implies, but something more fragmented and contested. In this sense, many organizations may be better understood as *CAS-like under certain conditions* rather than as complex adaptive systems in any full or stable sense—and the gap between the two is not merely empirical but purposive.

Limitations and Future Research

This paper has intentionally focused on the foundational texts and some of the most frequently cited examples in complexity leadership. These works shape much of the field's discourse, and clarifying their internal inconsistencies is a necessary first step before turning to broader reviews or new empirical studies. Future research might extend this critique by examining how CAS is applied across different organizational contexts and domains and by testing whether the conceptual issues identified here continue to surface in practice.

Overall, the analysis suggests that CAS should not be treated as a settled organizational reality. Rather, it is better understood as an idealized state or latent potential that organizations may approach under particular conditions. Recognizing this distinction can help sharpen the use of CAS in leadership studies and encourage greater care in distinguishing between metaphorical and empirical claims.

References

- Ashmos, D. P., Duchon, D., & McDaniel, R. R. (2000). Organizational responses to complexity: The effect on organizational performance. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 13(6), 577-595. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09534810010378597>
- Author & ---- (xxxx). Work title. In Editor1 & Editor 2 (Eds.), xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx (pp. 11-28). Publisher.

- Benbya, H., & McKelvey, B. (2006). Toward a complexity theory of information systems development. *Information Technology & People*, 19(1), 12-34. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09593840610649952>
- Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2024). *34.7 percent of business establishments born in 2013 were still operating in 2023* (The Economics Daily). U.S. Department of Labor. Retrieved July 21, 2025, from <https://www.bls.gov/opub/ted/2024/34-7-percent-of-business-establishments-born-in-2013-were-still-operating-in-2023.htm>
- Covvey, H. D. (2018). Healthcare as a complex adaptive system. In H. Kip, N. Jong, L. Van Gemert-Pijnen, R. Sanderman, & S. M. Kelders (Eds.), *EHealth research, theory and development* (1st ed., pp. 69-90). Routledge.
- Cyert, R. M., & March, J. G. (1963). *A behavioral theory of the firm*. Prentice-Hall.
- Eoyang, G. H. (2009). *Coping with chaos: Seven simple tools* (1st ed.). Lagumo.
- Hazy, J. K., Goldstein, J. A., & Lichtenstein, B. B. (2007). Complex systems leadership theory: An introduction. In J. K. Hazy, J. A. Goldstein, & B. B. Lichtenstein (Eds.), *Complex systems leadership theory: New perspectives from complexity science on social and organizational effectiveness* (pp. 1-16). Exploring Organizational Compl.
- Heifetz, R. A. (1994). *Leadership without easy answers*. Harvard University Press.
- Hunt, C. (2022). A tipping point? Spirituality in a time of meta crisis. *Journal for the Study of Spirituality*, 12(1), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20440243.2022.2062149>

- Kilduff, M., Crossland, C., & Tsai, W. (2008). Pathways of opportunity in dynamic organizational networks. In M. Uhl-Bien & R. Marion (Eds.), *Complexity leadership: Part 1: Conceptual foundations* (pp. 97-114). IAP.
- Lencioni, P. M. (2007). *The five dysfunctions of a team: Participant workbook*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Lissack, M. R. (1999). Complexity: The science, its vocabulary, and its relation to organizations. *Emergence*, 1(1), 110-126. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327000em0101_7
- Mannix, E., & Neale, M. A. (2005). What differences make a difference? *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 6(2), 31-55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1529-1006.2005.00022.x>
- McKelvey, B. (2008). Emergent strategy via complexity leadership: Using complexity science and adaptive tension to build distributed intelligence. In M. Uhl-Bien & R. Marion (Eds.), *Complexity leadership: Part 1: Conceptual foundations* (pp. 239-282). IAP.
- Merton, R. K. (1936). The unanticipated consequences of purposive social action. *American Sociological Review*, 1(6), 894. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2084615>
- Pype, P., Mertens, F., Helewaut, F., & Krystallidou, D. (2018). Healthcare teams as complex adaptive systems: Understanding team behaviour through team members' perception of interpersonal interaction. *BMC Health Services Research*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3392-3>
- Quade, K., & Holladay, R. (2010). *Dynamical leadership: Building adaptive capacity for uncertain times*. CreateSpace.

Rittel, H. W., & Webber, M. M. (1973). Dilemmas in a general theory of planning. *Policy Sciences*, 4(2), 155-169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01405730>

Schneider, M., & Somers, M. (2006). Organizations as complex adaptive systems: Implications of complexity theory for leadership research. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 17(4), 351-365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2006.04.006>

Tooze, A. (2022, October 22). Welcome to the world of the polycrisis. *Financial Times*.

Uhl-Bien, M., Marion, R., & McKelvey, B. (2007). Complexity leadership theory: Shifting leadership from the Industrial Age to the knowledge era. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 18(4), 298-318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2007.04.002>

Uhl-Bien, M., & Marion, R. (2008). *Complexity leadership: Part 1: Conceptual foundations*. IAP.

Uhl-Bien, M., & Marion, R. (2008). Introduction. In M. Uhl-Bien & R. Marion (Eds.), *Complexity leadership: Part 1: Conceptual foundations* (pp. 1-14). IAP.

Uhl-Bien, M., & Marion, R. (2009). Complexity leadership in bureaucratic forms of organizing: A meso model. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 20(4), 631-650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2009.04.007>

Watts, D. J., & Strogatz, S. H. (1998). Collective dynamics of ‘small-world’ networks. *Nature*, 393(6684), 440-442. <https://doi.org/10.1038/30918>